

THE CONTROL OF OSCILLATORY MODES IN A BANG-BANG TRACKER

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Abstract

Phase plane methods are developed for the analysis of oscillations in pulsed systems which can be modeled as sampled-data bang-bang systems. The methodology is graphical and provides a base for the synthesis of lead compensation networks for controlling the oscillatory problem.

Introduction

The objective of this paper is to present an analysis, by means of an example, of simple lead compensation on moding in a sampled-data bang-bang system with second order plant dynamics. A laser tracker is a system where the control of moding is of concern and will be used as an example.

A laser tracker designed to track a point which is being illuminated by a pulsed laser whose pulse repetition rate is f , and which employs a quadrant detector on a gimbaled platform, yields the best steady state pointing accuracy when its oscillations about the null point are constrained to a frequency of $f/2$. This oscillatory mode is the primary mode. However, since the tracker is nonlinear its response is input dependent and steady state oscillations in modes other than the primary mode can occur. This is shown using phase plane methods in the following section followed by an example where lead compensation is used to eliminate the problem. The problem as presented is constrained to tracker motion in one plane.

Moding in a Sampled Data Bang-Bang Tracker

Figure 1 is a block diagram of the system being considered. It is assumed that the target being tracked is located along the null axis of the sensor/platform combination; that is along the caged (boresight) optical axis thus providing an initial pointing error of zero. The nonlinearity is bang-bang and represents the laser detector and signal processing in one plane. The sample and hold representation models the fact that the information to the platform is via the reception of a pulsed laser spot. Reflected energy falls on one side of the detector thus setting a signal of predetermined amplitude whose polarity remains constant for at least one time interval $T=1/f$. The remaining blocks depict dynamics associated with the gimbaled platform.

Figure 1. System block diagram.

Figure 2 is a signal flow graph representation of Figure 1. The use of this signal flow graph is documented in Reference 1 and an understanding of such is necessary for the reading of this paper.

The point in time at which the system is released is denoted as t_0 . The value of $c(t=t_0)$ determines $m(t)$, which in this example is -1 or +1 for at least one laser pulse interval T . The states $v(t)$ and $c(t)$ can be computed over one laser pulse interval by using $m(t)$ and the initial conditions $v(t_0)$ and $c(t_0)$. The following uses Figure 2 for deriving the system's phase plane equation.

Application of Mason's gain formula to the signal flow graph yields,

$$C(s) = \frac{c_0}{s} + \frac{v_0}{s(s+a)} + \frac{Km_0}{s^2(s+a)}, \quad (1)$$

$$V(s) = \frac{v_0}{s+a} + \frac{Km_0}{s(s+a)}, \quad (2)$$

where c_0 , v_0 , m_0 denote values at $t=t_0$. The inverse Laplace is

$$c(t) = c_0 + \left(\frac{1}{a} - \frac{1}{a} e^{-a(t-t_0)} \right) v_0 - \left(\frac{1}{a} (t-t_0) - \frac{1}{a^2} + \frac{1}{a^2} e^{-a(t-t_0)} \right) Km_0, \quad (3)$$

$$v(t) = e^{-a(t-t_0)} v_0 + \left(\frac{1}{a} - \frac{1}{a} e^{-a(t-t_0)} \right) Km_0. \quad (4)$$

Figure 3. Trajectory depicting a double mode situation.

Figure 4. System with lead compensation.

Figure 5. Figure 4 redrawn.

The utility of this is shown by a continuation of the preceding example. Select n as 10 and allow the rest of the problem parameters to remain the same. Equation (13) is drawn in the phase plane in Figure 6 and provides a boundary below which the error signal, e , is positive and above which it is negative. The trajectory starts from the point of initial conditions, $c_0 = v_0 = 0.0$, until it intercepts the switching line. Since this point of intercept is above the error signal boundary line e is negative and likewise the selection of m is negative in the system's phase plane equation. The trajectory is continued until the next switching line is intercepted. Since this point is below the error signal boundary line e is positive and the trajectory changes rather than being continued as in Figure 3. It is now noted that the period of oscillation is $2T$ and the system is in the primary mode.

Figure 6. Trajectory with lead compensation.

Additional examples are given in Figures 7, 8, and 9. These examples are for the case where $K=a=1.0$ and r is a unit step input. The heavy lines in Figures 7 and 8 depict a double mode situation. Figure 9 shows a triple mode of period $6T$. The dashed line is the error signal boundary line for $n=0.7$ and the dashed trajectories are for the lead compensated cases. These examples were taken out of Reference 1.

The initial conditions for Figure 8 are such that equation (8) does not immediately apply because the term whose natural log is taken is initially negative. Equations (4) and (6) are used for obtaining the phase plane trajectory until equation (8) applies.

Figure 7. Double mode case.

Figure 9. Triple mode case.

Figure 8. Double mode case.

Conclusion

Careful examination of the examples given in this paper and others not presented here, coupled with analog computer modeling of the problem, sets a basis for the following conjecture.

Systems of the type modeled by Figure 1 for the autonomous and step input case can be constrained to primary mode oscillations by lead compensation when $n < a$ as defined in Figure 5.

References

1. B.C. Kuo, Analysis and Synthesis of Sampled-Data Control Systems, Prentice-Hall, 1963.